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Annex D Results of the survey

A survey was distributed among 18 fish health practitioners in Europe, aiming to collect information on implementation of measures to mitigate the risk of introduction of VHSV, IHNV and HPR-deleted ISAV. Participants were invited to share their practical experiences, thoughts on best practices and practical difficulties.

When answering the survey, participants were advised to consider that the measures described specifically concern establishments where fertilised eggs and/or gametes are produced or received.

A. GENERAL INFORMATION

1. Type of establishments

Number of respondents: 18/18

Thirteen (13) respondents indicated working in the private sector, either working for private companies or as an independent private field veterinarian. Two respondents indicated work in a competent authority, one in research/diagnostic, and one in academia.

2. Country/ies of operation

Number of respondents: 18/18

The responses highlight the extensive European coverage of respondents. Among the 18 respondents, 12 work in one country and 6 with more than one, with Norway being the country most represented (7).

3. Fish species reared in the establishment(s) visited

Number of respondents: 18/18

Among the 18 respondents, 6 work with both Rainbow trout and Atlantic salmon, 8 with Rainbow trout only and 4 with Atlantic Salmon only. Overall, 10 respondents work with Atlantic Salmon establishments, and 14 with Rainbow Trout establishments. The number of establishments visited by respondents was in general smaller for Atlantic salmon (less than 20, with only one

notable exception visiting >280 establishments) than for rainbow trout (less than 100, with only one exception visiting 101-153 establishments).

Number of respondents: 9/10

Number of respondents: 13/14

4. Establishment(s) visited which are provider of eyed eggs and/or receiver of eyed eggs

Respondents were asked to check whether the establishments they work with are providers or receivers of eyed eggs, (with option to check both answers); alternatively, they could indicate that the establishments they work with are neither providers nor receivers. Options also included not applicable or 'Other' (with free-text explanation).

Number of respondents: 18/18

Three (3) respondents reported working with providers only; 3 with receivers only; and 11 checked that they worked both with providers and with receivers. One respondent checked the option 'Other' and added the explanation 'central closed breeding colony, sometimes providing eggs to single farms'.

Number of respondents: 13/14

Number of respondents: 13/14

5. Establishments which are not receiver or provider

Respondents were also asked how many establishments they visit which are neither receiver nor providers.

Number of respondents: 14/18

Most of the respondents (10) work with a number of establishments that are not receivers or providers between 1 and 20, 3 with 50-65 establishments and only 1 is working with more than 150 establishments that are not receivers nor providers.

6. Establishment(s) visited in which Atlantic salmon broodstock have a sea water phase in open pens

Number of respondents: 10/10 (10 respondents who indicated working with Atlantic Salmon as per question 3)

Three (3) respondents answered that all of the Atlantic salmon establishments that they visit have a sea water phase in open pens, 2 that some of them have it, and 2 that none of them have a sea water phase in open pens. Although all 10 respondents previously reporting working with Atlantic Salmon establishments answered this question, 3 checked 'Not applicable', which meaning is unclear since these are indeed respondent working with Atlantic Salmon.

7. Establishment(s) visited in which rainbow trout broodstock have a sea water phase in open pens

Number of respondents: 14/14 (14 respondents who indicated working with rainbow trout as per question 3)

Most of the respondents (10) answered that none of the rainbow trout establishments that they visit have a sea water phase in open pens, while 2 replied that all of them have it, and 1 that some of them have it. One respondent checked 'Not applicable', although they had previously indicated working with rainbow trout.

8. Trade with other establishments and their health status:

Respondents were asked to indicate whether the establishments they work with provide or receive eggs to establishments of higher or lower health status, within or outside the country. They could check multiple options.

Number of respondents: 18/18

Almost all the respondents (17) work with a provider to the same or lower health status establishment within the Country, 11 work with a receiver from the same or higher health status

establishment outside the Country, 13 with a receiver from the same or higher health status establishment within the Country, 9 with a provider to the same or lower health status establishment outside the Country, and 1 with other type of establishments.

9. Health status of establishments or the zones/compartments they belong to – are they officially free from IHNV, VHSV, and/or HPR-deleted ISAV

Number of respondents: 18/18

Ten (10) respondents work with establishments free from all the 3 viruses, 5 with establishments free from VHSV/IHNV, 1 with establishments free from VHSV/ISAV and 2 with establishments free only from ISAV HPR deleted. Overall, 15 respondents work with establishments free of IHNV, 16 with VHSV free establishments and 13 with establishments free of HPR-deleted ISAV virus.

Respondents were also asked to indicate how many establishments they visit with officially free status or in zones recognized free. They answers are here summarized by pathogen:

Establishments free from VHSV:

Number of the respondents: 16/18

All respondents from Norway highlighted that the country is officially free from VHSV. Respondents in other countries reported varying number of recognized free establishments visited, from 10-25. One respondent highlighted that the egg provider establishments served are recognized free, while the receivers may not be.

Establishments free from IHNV:

Number of respondents: 15/18

Responses were in general the same as for above, including the status of free in Norway.

Establishments free from HPR-deleted ISAV:

Number of respondents: 13/18

Comparison with the number of reported free establishments and each respondents' previous reported number of establishments served allowed conclusion that at least 8 of the respondents work solely with establishments recognized free. Five other respondents reported serving between 13-30 establishments recognized free.

B. TESTING OF BROODSTOCK

In this section respondents were asked to consider two main types of production separately: those in which broodstock fish stay their entire life in fresh water (F), and those in which broodstock fish can also stay part of their life in sea water (S). Respondents were instructed to answer questions only for the production type that applies to the establishments they visit, and if they visit both types, to consider each of these types independently and answer each dedicated section accordingly.

Within each section dedicated to each of these production types, respondents encountered the same questions related to individual testing of broodstock at stripping, and population testing.

Broodstock fish that stay their entire life in fresh water (F)

(F) 1. Individual testing at stripping

Participants were asked to indicate, for each of the three viruses independently, whether broodfish are individually sampled at stripping. The answers for the 12 participants who responded to this question are shown below per virus:

	VHSV	IHNV	HPR- deleted ISAV
Yes, broodfish are samples and EVERY fish is tested	0	0	1
Yes, but only a subset of them are tested	7	7	3
NO	5	5	8
Respondents = 12			

Respondents were also asked to specify whether the answer varies among the establishments they visit, and explain the main differences.

The 11 respondents pointed out that in countries officially free from EU listed diseases (infection with VHSV, IHNV, HPRΔ ISAV) broodfish are not normally tested at stripping. The testing

practices vary significantly and are influenced by the production scale and the regulatory requirements. In disease-free zones or compartments, testing is often related to national surveillance or specific export demands. Some facilities focus on preventive measures like egg disinfection over testing.

Survey participants were asked if **samples are pooled for testing**, for VHSV and IHNV only 7 participants responded, all of which indicated that if sampling is done, these are grouped into pools of 10 samples. For HPR-deleted ISAV, only 5 responded, 3 of which indicated that pooling is done (again in pools of 10 samples) and 2 of which indicated pooling is not used.

Participants were also asked which matrices are sampled for testing.

From the 7 respondents, 5 participants work with establishments that use more than one type of sample for testing (Internal organs + ovarian fluids; internal organs + ovarian fluids + others) while the other 2 use just one type of sample (1 internal organs and 1 ovarian fluids). Overall, 6 respondents use internal organs for sampling, 6 use ovarian fluids and 1 uses another type of sample (water filtered and egg surface swabs).

Lastly, participants were asked to list where the major bottlenecks, difficulties or common failures are encountered when implementing individual testing of broodfish. They were also asked to describe and explain any difference among establishments.

Ten participants shared their views.

The answers highlight that the major bottlenecks for individual broodfish testing are logistical problems (availability of the screening equipment and in general difficulty of individual screening) and the high costs related to individual testing. Small farms struggle most due to limited staff, low egg volumes, and cost-benefit issues. Differences arise between large, regulated establishments and smaller or wild-stock-based facilities, where testing is rare or neglected. Climate change (warmer water) and laboratory constraints (e.g. sample types, turnaround time) add complexity. Inexperienced personnel and lack of awareness, especially in farms focusing on restocking programs, are common points of failure across regions. In this type of production (mainly related to rainbow trout) the participants also pointed out that eggs are not kept separated for each pair of parents and therefore cannot be traced back to individual parents.

Overall, the results showed that individual testing at stripping is not a common practice in this type of production.

(F) 2. Population testing

Participants were asked to indicate, for each of the three viruses independently, whether the fish population in the establishment are tested to assess the health status during production of the broodstock. The answers for the 12 participants who responded to this question are shown below per virus:

	VHSV	IHNV	HPR- deleted ISAV
YES	11	11	6
NO	1	1	5
empty	0	0	1
Respondents = 12			

Asked about the **sampling size and the frequency of the sampling**, the 10 respondents to the question just referred to existing legislation, pointing to a general number of 30 fish per year

(which is the maintenance sample cited in legislation, which also requires testing of 75 fish two times a year in the first two years- in order to achieve approval as VHSV or IHNV free establishments). Exceptional cases were listed in which establishments test more frequently due to demands from clients to which they provide eggs. Participants highlighted that testing also varies according to the scale of production and historical health status of the establishment, and that population testing is complemented by clinical surveillance (more testing can be applied in case of disease suspicion).

Participants were asked to list points where major bottlenecks, difficulties or common failures are encountered when implementing population testing of broodfish. They were also asked to describe and explain any difference among establishments.

Ten participants shared their views. They reported that population testing faces challenges like high costs, scheduling and coordination issues, and incomplete sampling of all year classes or production units. Underreporting of outbreaks occurs due to reputation concerns and perceived lack of treatment options. Smaller farms, especially in lower-risk zones, can neglect testing, mainly driven by cost. Sampling wild broodstock is difficult due to availability and genetic concerns. Delays in test results and environmental factors (e.g., weather, wildlife) further complicate effective surveillance.

(F) 3. Re-use of broodfish after stripping

Number of the respondents: 12/18

All the respondents answered that the broodfish is reused for reproduction after stripping.

Respondents were also asked to describe and explain any difference among establishments:

Ten participants shared their experience, reporting that practices vary widely: some establishments euthanize broodfish after a single stripping, especially larger or export-oriented companies, while others reuse fish for multiple years (2–6 years) of egg production. Biosecurity measures, such as closed water supplies and farm isolation, support reuse in many cases. Overall, both single-use and multi-use strategies coexist depending on company size and market demands. As one participant summarized: 'The greatest variability in the approach is given by the size of the company and above all by the reference markets'.

Broodstock fish that stay part of their life in seawater (S)

(S) 1. Individual testing at stripping

Participants were asked to indicate, for each of the three viruses independently, whether broodfish are individually sampled at stripping. The answers for the 8 participants who responded to this question are shown below per virus:

	VHSV	IHNV	HPR- deleted ISAV
Yes, broodfish are samples and EVERY fish is tested	0	0	4
Yes, but only a subset of them are tested	4	4	4
NO	4	4	0
Respondents = 8			

Respondents were also asked to specify whether the answer varies among the establishments they visit, and explain the main differences.

The 6 respondents reported that sampling practices vary widely and are largely driven by customer and importing region requirements, with testing often risk-based rather than mandatory. Individual testing is typically done in fresh-water broodstock stations using ovarian fluid (pooled samples) or in milt (individual tests), with additional organ testing for surveillance. Farms maintaining disease-free status follow strict protocols, especially when using wild broodstock, with annual testing of batches. Overall, the approach depends heavily on production scale, health history, and market demands.

Asked if **samples are pooled for testing**, for VHSV and IHNV only 4 responded, half of which indicated pooling (10 samples), and half of which indicated no pooling. For HPR-deleted ISAV, 6 responded, 4 of which indicated no pooling and 2 indicated pooling.

Participants were also asked which matrices are sampled for testing.

All 8 respondents replied that they use ovarian fluids for testing, and 7 of them are also using internal organs. Two of the respondents are also using other types of samples (milt from males; water and biofilm).

Lastly, participants were asked to list points where major bottlenecks, difficulties or common failures are encountered when implementing individual testing of broodfish. They were also asked to describe and explain any difference among establishments.

Seven participants shared their views.

Key challenges included the need for sufficient single-parent incubator capacity to keep eggs separated until test results arrive, which can be delayed, increasing contamination risk. Rapid results are crucial but often not feasible, complicating handling and transport logistics. Costs and fear of disease detection reducing sales also hinder testing uptake. Sampling is sometimes done by less-trained personnel, affecting quality. Non-lethal milt testing faces technical issues like PCR inhibitors, making it difficult to implement broadly, especially in smaller or less-equipped farms.

(S) 2. Population testing

Participants were asked to indicate, for each of the three viruses independently, whether the fish population in the establishment are tested to assess the health status during production of the broodstock. The answers are shown below per virus:

	VHSV	IHNV	HPR- deleted ISAV
Yes	3	3	7
No	3	3	1
Respondents	6		8

Asked about the **sampling size and the frequency of the sampling**, for VHSV and IHNV 3 respondents again mentioned the regulated maintenance sample of 30 fish per year (or twice a year). More respondents answered for HPR-deleted ISAV – 7 in total. The majority of the respondents (4) tests more than 100 fishes per year (10 per month or all the dead fishes the last 9 month before stripping), one tests 30 yearly, one 30 two times per year (60) and another 20 every third month (80).

Participants were asked to explain differences among establishments.

Seven participants shared their views. According to their answers, sampling size and frequency vary widely depending on company policy, country regulations, and health status of the establishment. Many companies test broodstock during the seawater phase before moving fish

to land-based units, with sample sizes ranging around 20–30 fish annually as a minimal maintenance protocol. In some countries, like Norway, VHSV and IHNV testing is part of national surveillance to maintain disease-free status, while ISAV testing is risk-based and influenced by customer demands. Overall, testing frequency and sample size depend on scale, historical health status, and whether the farm is in an officially disease-free zone.

Participants were asked to list points where major bottlenecks, difficulties or common failures are encountered when implementing population testing of broodfish. They were also asked to describe and explain any difference among establishments.

Only three participants responded. They shared that key difficulties include insufficient sample sizes in some operations, which may not be statistically robust, especially in regions with multiple farms where health status can fluctuate. Testing for ISAV HPR0 is critical but often overlooked, posing a risk for ISAV deleted strain management. Cost is a significant barrier, with some establishments limiting testing frequency due to expense and fear of disease detection affecting sales. Overall, challenges relate to balancing thorough surveillance with practical and financial constraints.

(S) 3. Re-use of broodfish after stripping

Number of respondents: 8/18

Six (6) respondents do not re-use broodfish for reproduction after stripping while the other two do.

Specific explanations and differences among establishments were generally not provided by participants, but one reported that establishments may cull all females, but re-use some males.

C. DISINFECTION OF EGGS

(P) Disinfection of eggs at the origin (producer establishment)

(P) 1. Is disinfection with iodine applied to eggs at the origin?

Number of respondents: 17/18

Most of the respondents said that the disinfection is applied to all the produced eggs (9) or on a part of the produced eggs (7). Only one respondent said that they do not perform the disinfection because of time, labour and disinfectant costs, including the cost of disposing of the used chemicals.

Those answering 'yes, to a part of the produced eggs' or 'no' were asked to provide **further explanations as to why**

disinfection was not applied to all eggs. Six (6) respondents described that iodine disinfection is mainly applied to eggs leaving central broodstock facilities, especially those destined for export, as a key biosecurity measure. Practices vary due to differing national

regulations and product authorizations within the EU. Small farms often skip disinfection for locally used eggs, especially when operating in disease-free zones, relying on their health status as justification. Overall, disinfection is targeted primarily at eggs with higher transmission risk, such as those moving between regions or countries.

Asked to describe and explain any difference among and within establishments, 11 respondents described that most establishments apply iodine disinfection to eggs, also for other purposes such as preventing other infections such as saprolegniosis. While a standard protocol including rinsing in saline before disinfection is common, some differences exist based on management decisions, market requirements, and farm size. Larger producers and those working with wild broodstock tend to have stricter and more frequent disinfection protocols, sometimes using multiple disinfectants. Smaller or nationally focused farms may skip or simplify the iodine treatment, often due to perceived virus-free status or cost/time savings. Compliance with WOAHP iodine protocols varies, but most record disinfection success regarding fungal contamination and egg survival.

(P) 2. At which stages is disinfection applied?

Number of respondents: 16/18

Only 4 respondents apply disinfection in only one stage, the eyed eggs stage. The other 12 respondents indicated that disinfection is applied both to green eggs and to eyed eggs.

Participants were asked to explain the **reasons why disinfection could be applied just once**. Most of the 10 respondents to this question answered that further egg disinfection can sometimes be considered potentially harmful by producers. Many farms limit disinfection to a single application due to concerns over egg mortality, deformities or practical difficulties like product availability. However, some establishments perform disinfection twice—once as green eggs after fertilisation and again at the eyed stage—especially when eggs are transferred between farms. Practices vary based on management preferences, legislation, and local experience, with some farms expecting the receiving farm to disinfect again.

Asked to explain their **experience with the stages when disinfection is applied**, 6 respondents shared that disinfection is often applied twice (once at the green egg stage shortly after fertilisation and again at the eyed egg stage, especially before shipment). However, practices vary among facilities; some apply iodine only once at the eyed egg stage. Additional daily disinfection with other bactericides or virucides may also be performed during incubation. Alternative disinfectants like peracetic acid or peroxide-based products are increasingly used, particularly before transport, sometimes with low residues left in transport water to enhance biosecurity.

(P) 3. Is the eggs disinfection protocol recommended by WOAHP used?

Number of respondents: 16/18

Fifteen (15) respondents visit establishments that use the egg disinfection protocol recommended by WOAHP, 10 in all farms visited, and 5 in some of them. Only one respondent reported using a modification of the protocol: 10 ppm iodine for an hour (lower concentration, longer time).

The respondents stated that most producers follow the WOAHP-recommended iodine disinfection protocol, usually applied to newly fertilised or eyed eggs according to their establishment manuals. While the protocol is generally accepted as best practice, some farmers skip or deviate

from it, often due to a perceived low risk. Inspectors review protocols and recommend corrections when deviations occur, but compliance varies among farms.

(P) 4. Describe any weakness/impracticalities/losses/side effects in the disinfection protocol recommended by WOAH

Number of the respondents: 13/18

According to respondents, the WOAH egg disinfection protocol is generally considered effective if applied correctly, but practical challenges exist. Key issues include inconsistent availability or use of pathogen-free saline for rinsing, uncertainty around precise iodine concentrations and rinsing times, and difficulty integrating the minimum 10-minute exposure into production workflows. Some farmers skip or shorten rinsing steps, viewing them as unnecessary. Additionally, regulatory uncertainties in the EU about iodine use pose potential risks for hatchery operations and exports. Overall, respondents while the protocol is sound, implementation gaps and regulatory hurdles create weaknesses in practice.

(R) Disinfection of eggs at the destination (receiver establishment)

(R) 1. Is disinfection with iodine applied to eggs at destination?

Number of respondents: 17/18

Sixteen (16) respondents replied that they visit establishments that apply the disinfection with iodine to eggs at the destination, 11 of them to a part of the produced eggs and 5 to all the produced eggs. One respondent answered not working with farms that disinfect at destination because most of the receivers rely on disinfection applied before delivery by the producers, frequently fearing to cause damage to their egg batch.

Asked to give **further descriptions and insights on the practice**, 11

respondents explained that disinfection of eggs at destination varies widely and is often decided by the receiving company. Many rely on the producer's disinfection, especially when eggs come from large, trusted suppliers, while smaller suppliers' eggs are more likely to be disinfected upon arrival. Challenges such as timing (e.g., eggs close to hatching), labor, costs, and availability of authorized disinfectants limit consistent application. Some facilities with lower biosecurity or specific incubation methods may skip disinfection, and alternative disinfectants are increasingly used instead of iodine.

(R) 2. Is the eggs disinfection protocol recommended by WOAH used?

Number of respondents: 16/18

All the respondents work in establishments where they use the disinfection protocol recommended by WOAH, 10 of them in all of the farms and 6 in some of the farms.

They also reported that receiving hatcheries typically disinfect eyed eggs with iodine for 10 minutes prior to incubation. In addition, many also use or supplement iodine disinfection with alternative substances such as peracetic acid or peroxide-based disinfectants.

(R) 3. Describe any weakness/impracticalities/losses/side effects in the disinfection protocol recommended by WOAH

Number of the respondents: 14/18

Most respondents find the WOAH disinfection protocol adequate if applied correctly but reported that challenges exist such as inconsistent availability of authorized iodine products and difficulties ensuring pathogen-free saline for rinsing. Timing and proper understanding of clean versus dirty areas can be problematic, especially when eggs are near hatching, as disinfection can reduce survival rates. Operational constraints, like limited labor and large egg volumes, often make strict adherence difficult. Some farms adopt alternative disinfectants (e.g., peracetic acid, povidone) with modified exposure and rinsing practices to simplify routines. Overall, while the protocol is largely accepted, practical implementation varies.

(M) Disinfection of milt

Participants were asked to share their opinion about whether, in case of importation of frozen milt, they thought it would be feasible to apply disinfection to fertilised eggs after using the imported milt.

Among the 13 respondents, most agreed that disinfecting fertilised eggs after using imported frozen milt is feasible and advisable as a biosecurity measure. While the true risk of pathogen transmission via frozen milt is considered low, disinfection helps reduce surface contaminants and other pathogens, improving overall egg survival. The practice aligns with protocols used for fresh milt, and concerns about damage to eggs are generally minimal. A few noted limited direct experience but concurred that disinfection remains beneficial regardless of milt source.

D. CRITICAL POINTS

The note/comments provided by the fish health practitioners on major bottlenecks for implementation, difficulties in adoption, common failures or best practices for each of the critical points listed in Table C.1 in Annex C have been summarised in section 3.5.3 of the scientific opinion. Note that Table C.1 in Annex C corresponds to Table 10 in the scientific opinion.